

A Review of 2D Diffusion Methods for 3D Medical Image Synthesis

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Abstract

3D medical image synthesis using diffusion models has shown great promise, but training and deploying native 3D architectures remains resource-intensive and computationally demanding. As a result, 2D approaches are gaining popularity due to their efficiency, scalability, and ease of deployment. However, these methods often suffer from inter-slice inconsistency, leading to discontinuities and artefacts in the reconstructed 3D volumes. To address this, a growing body of work has introduced various strategies, each with different assumptions, design choices, and degrees of success. In this review, we provide a comprehensive overview of state-of-the-art 2D diffusion-based methods that aim to enforce inter-slice consistency in 3D medical image generation. We categorize these methods into three main groups: condition-guided techniques, architectural innovations, and post-generation optimization strategies. By organizing and analyzing these approaches, we highlight key trends, challenges, and future directions in the pursuit of anatomically coherent and computationally efficient 3D synthesis.

Keywords: 3D Medical Image Synthesis, Diffusion Models, Inter-Slice Consistency, Conditional Diffusion, Architectural Innovations, Computational Efficiency, Volumetric Coherence

1. Introduction

Synthetic medical images are increasingly valuable in medical imaging, addressing issues like data scarcity and privacy concerns by providing large datasets for research and development [1]. The advent of deep learning, particularly Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [2], has revolutionized this field by enabling the generation of high-quality synthetic medical images. This is particularly important in scenarios where acquiring real medical images is expensive, time-consuming, or exposes patients to increased radiation [3] [4]. Initially, Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) [5] were explored for image synthesis, but GANs [2] have since demonstrated superior performance in generating realistic images, especially in tasks like image synthesis, reconstruction, and cross-modality generation [6] [7] [8]. However, recent advancements in diffusion models [9] have introduced a more robust alternative, which addresses some of the challenges inherent in GANs, such as training instability and mode collapse [10].

Some efforts in medical image generation have focused on 2D images, such as chest X-rays or slice-wise 2D axial images of 3D volumes. Even when the goal is to generate 3D volumes, one approach is to generate individual 2D slices that are later stacked together to form a 3D representation of anatomical structures [3][11]. This slice-wise approach, being more com-

putationally efficient than native 3D generation, remains a popular choice, especially in scenarios with limited computational resources. However, generating slices independently introduces the challenge of inter-slice inconsistency, where adjacent slices may vary in style, structure, or alignment, degrading the quality and clinical viability of the reconstructed 3D image.

Figure 1: The challenge of inter-slice consistency in CT-to-MRI translation using different methods. The input CT image is shown alongside outputs from Palette [12] and Slice-Consistent Brownian Bridge Diffusion Model (SC-BBDM) [13], with the ground truth (GT) MRI for reference. The top row presents axial views, while the second row displays sagittal views. The highlighted yellow boxes emphasize anatomical inconsistencies in the synthetic images, where Palette exhibits substantial structural artefacts, while SC-BBDM demonstrates improved anatomical coherence and intensity preservation.

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Inter-slice inconsistency is not only a challenge in synthetic image generation but also occurs during 3D medical image ac-

quisition. For instance, in short-axis cardiac MRI (CMR), slice misalignment can occur due to variations in breath-holding during consecutive image acquisitions, leading to significant misalignment in the reconstructed 3D volumes [14]. Similarly, stair-step artefacts are common in CT imaging, where inconsistencies between slices arise from the use of thick and non-overlapping slices, resulting in discontinuities in multi-planar or 3D reconstructions [15]. Addressing these inconsistencies is critical to ensure that the generated or acquired 3D images are accurate, reliable, and suitable for clinical applications. Various methods, such as motion correction and deep learning-based techniques, have been explored to mitigate these issues in both image acquisition and generation [16] [17]. Although inter-slice inconsistency is relevant to both image acquisition and generation, the scope of this review is confined to addressing inter-slice inconsistencies in synthetic image generation.

Although there has been growing interest in generating native 3D medical volumes, current efforts using diffusion models require significant computational resources, including high-end GPUs and vast datasets. For example, the 3D-MedDiffusion framework [18] trains its Patch-Volume Autoencoder in two stages (patch-wise and volume-wise) on a single A100 GPU with 80 GB of memory, while its core diffusion model is trained on eight A100 GPUs. Given these constraints, many researchers continue to rely on enhanced 2D-based solutions that are more computationally feasible. These approaches incorporate contextual conditioning or architectural innovations to address inter-slice inconsistency without requiring extensive resources.

Figure 1 provides an example of typical 2D based image synthesis methods [13]. The synthetic MRI images were generated through an image-to-image translation task with CT images as input. A comparison is made between Palette [12], a pure 2D translation approach, and SC-BBDM, a Brownian bridge-based diffusion model enhanced with mechanisms for improved consistency. The Palette method exhibits significant structural artefacts, including horizontal streaking and loss of fine anatomical details. In contrast, SC-BBDM produces images that are visually closer to the ground truth, with better structural continuity and reduced intensity discrepancies across various plane reformations.

In this review, we provide a structured categorization of diffusion-based techniques and their associated evaluation methods for medical image generation. Our analysis is grounded in a comprehensive, systematic search of the Compendex, Inspec, PubMed, and Google Scholar databases and covers peer-reviewed articles published between 2020 and 2025 resulting in a total of 13 2D methods. We include works that use diffusion processes ranging from noise-driven generative models to image-to-image translation, with a focus on 2D methods that aim to synthesize coherent 3D medical volumes. Particular attention is paid to strategies that enforce inter-slice consistency, a critical challenge when extending 2D models to volumetric data. By synthesizing and organizing existing work into a unified taxonomy, this review clarifies the design landscape of diffusion models in medical imaging, maps prevailing trends, pinpoints methodological limitations, exposes gaps in evaluation, and raises open research questions, providing a timely roadmap

for future research and development as the field continues to evolve.

To this end, we group existing methods into three main categories as follows: (i) Condition-guided methods, which inject auxiliary information such as masks or reference slices into the diffusion process; (ii) Architectural innovations, which modify the network structure to capture volumetric context more effectively; and (iii) Post-generation optimization, which applies consistency constraints after sampling.

Across all three methodological categories, we list and explain the evaluation metrics reported in the literature. We further group these metrics into three families: referenced quantitative metrics, which compare each synthetic image or volume with a paired ground-truth reference and report pixel- or feature-level fidelity, non-referenced quantitative metrics, which operate without ground-truth images and estimate realism directly from the distributional properties of the generated data, and downstream or anatomical metrics, which assess how well the synthetic data support clinical tasks or preserve anatomical structure, such as Dice score for downstream segmentation tasks.

Prior surveys have reviewed diffusion models in medical imaging. A comprehensive survey of diffusion models across diverse imaging tasks including reconstruction, segmentation, and synthesis is presented in [19], whereas our work narrows the scope to 2D strategies for 3D synthesis and introduces a taxonomy specifically for inter-slice consistency. A benchmarking study comparing latent diffusion and GAN-based models in multimodal synthesis is reported in [20]; however, this does not address cross-slice coherence. A modality-specific review of diffusion applications in MRI is provided in [21], while our work is modality-agnostic and systematically categorizes 2D-to-3D strategies. Finally, [22] surveys diffusion in reconstruction tasks such as CT, PET, and MRI, with an emphasis on physics-informed priors; in contrast, we focus on image synthesis and explicitly emphasize evaluation of inter-slice consistency in 2D-based 3D pipelines.

The following is the list of the contributions of this review paper.

- We provide a unified taxonomy that covers condition-guided, architectural, and post-generation strategies for diffusion-based 2D-to-3D medical image synthesis.
- We offer a consolidated overview of categorized evaluation metrics with commentary on their relevance to inter-slice consistency and volumetric quality assessment.
- We expand our work with a critical analysis that surfaces common methodological limitations and outlines emerging trends in enforcing cross-slice coherence.
- We offer practical recommendations and future research directions aimed at closing current gaps in evaluation and benchmarking.

Figure 2 provides an overview of the methods discussed in this paper.

Figure 2: Summary of Categorized and Reviewed 2D Diffusion Methods

2. Review Methodology and Reproducibility

This work is a review article rather than the proposal of a new machine learning method, and therefore aspects such as dataset partitioning, cross-validation, or code release do not directly apply. Reproducibility is instead ensured through the transparency of our review process.

We conducted structured searches across multiple databases (Compendex, Inspec, PubMed, and Google Scholar) covering the years 2020–2025. Clear inclusion criteria were applied: only peer-reviewed works employing 2D diffusion models for 3D medical image synthesis with an emphasis on inter-slice consistency were retained. This process resulted in a final set of 13 methods. Figures reproduced from prior works are fully cited.

To make our survey reproducible and extensible, we (i) organize methods into a three-part taxonomy (condition-guided, architectural, and post-generation), (ii) provide a standardized summary of their computational requirements, and (iii) catalogue all reported evaluation metrics, grouping them into referenced, non-referenced, downstream, and anatomical families.

All results and figures discussed are drawn based on previously published studies. Potential biases primarily stem from the datasets used in those primary studies (e.g., limited cohort sizes, modality imbalance, or lack of demographic diversity). While such biases cannot be corrected at the review level, we mitigate their influence by focusing on methodological trends rather than absolute performance values.

Through this transparent search strategy, explicit inclusion rules, standardized taxonomy, and consolidated reporting, we aim to ensure that our findings can be replicated and extended by other researchers.

3. Background

3.1. Diffusion Methods for Volumetric Image Generation

As shown in Figure 3, diffusion models invert a gradual noising process: a clean instance x_0 is repeatedly perturbed by Gaussian noise, yielding a nearly isotropic latent $x_T \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$. A neural network $\epsilon_\theta(x_t, t)$ learns to predict the injected noise at

every discrete time-step. At inference the model follows the learned *reverse* Markov chain

$$x_{t-1} = f_\theta(x_t, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(x_t - \frac{1-\alpha_t}{\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_\theta(x_t, t) \right) + \sigma_t z, \quad z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), \quad (1)$$

where x_t and x_{t-1} are the noisy samples at steps t and $t-1$; $\alpha_t = 1 - \beta_t$ is the retained signal power, $\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{s=1}^t \alpha_s$ is the cumulative signal power, ϵ_θ predicts the added noise, σ_t is the sampler’s stochastic variance (e.g. $\sigma_t = \sqrt{\beta_t}$), and z is fresh Gaussian noise. Equation (1) is the original DDPM sampler and setting $\sigma_t = 0$ yields its deterministic DDIM counterpart.

Native 3D diffusion models operate directly on voxel grids, capturing complete volumetric context and producing anatomically coherent outputs. The hardware burden is severe: training commonly requires multi-node clusters equipped with high-memory GPUs such as NVIDIA A100 80 GB, and runs for several days. Many studies still resample input volumes to coarser voxel spacing to fit GPU memory constraints, underscoring the resource-intensive nature of native 3D DDPM architectures.

Latent Diffusion Models (LDMs) curb this bottleneck by performing diffusion in a compressed 3D latent grid generated by a separately trained auto-encoder (e.g. a VQ-GAN). Although 10–100× lighter in memory, LDM pipelines remain compute-hungry when high-resolution latents, multi-stage diffusion schedules, or large autoregressive priors are employed. Compression can also blur fine anatomical details, potentially jeopardising clinical reliability.

Naïve 2D slice-wise diffusion discards 3D context entirely by processing independent axial, coronal, or sagittal slices and the stacked outputs suffer visible inter-slice artefacts. Recent work therefore augments 2D models with explicit inter-slice constraints. These consistency-aware 2D approaches preserve 2D efficiency while enforcing volumetric coherence and form the primary focus of this review.

Table 1 contrasts the algorithmic design space of these four strategy families highlighting their core ideas, hardware advantages, and inherent limitations, whereas Table 2 summarises concrete native 3D and latent diffusion implementations reported

in the literature. When multiple datasets are used, the reported image shape in Table 2 corresponds to the dataset with the highest voxel count; for multi-stage models, the GPU with the greatest resource demand across stages is listed.

Figure 3: The forward (noise-injecting) and reverse (denoising) Markov chains in a diffusion model. The fixed forward process q gradually corrupts a clean sample x_0 with Gaussian noise over T steps to reach a nearly isotropic latent x_T . A neural network parameterises the reverse process p_θ , which successively removes noise, transforming x_T back to a realistic sample \tilde{x}_0 . Solid arrows denote analytically defined transitions; dashed arrows denote learned transitions.

3.2. Evaluation Methods

This section lists and explains the evaluation metrics used across different methods. Evaluation metrics can be broadly categorized into referenced metrics, which require ground-truth data, and non-referenced metrics, which assess image quality without ground truth. In addition, some studies gauge the utility of synthetic images for downstream tasks by reporting segmentation scores such as Dice similarity coefficient and Hausdorff distance, while others report anatomical measurements extracted from the synthetic volumes (e.g., mean cortical thickness).

Table 3 catalogues the metrics reported in diffusion-based image-translation studies, grouped into four classes: referenced image fidelity (RM), non-referenced perceptual realism (NM), downstream task performance (DM), and anatomical relevance (AM). Each entry lists its abbreviation, full metric name, and a short remark describing the property it measures, enabling consistent comparison across publications.

3D voxel-based reference metrics, for example volumetric averages of absolute or squared error or structural similarity measures, do penalise large mis-registrations, yet they remain an incomplete proxy for through-plane coherence. Because they compress per-voxel deviations into a single statistic, fine slice-to-slice jitter can be masked by large homogeneous regions and still yield an apparently high or low score. They are also insensitive to anatomical ordering: a volume whose axial slices are randomly permuted preserves the same marginal voxel distribution and can therefore attain a favourable value even though the sequence is anatomically impossible. Moreover, unpaired synthesis tasks, such as medical image translation, offer no voxel-aligned ground truth, making any reference metric inapplicable.

Non-reference metrics on the other hand assess global distributional or perceptual similarity but are likewise blind to slice ordering. They usually treat each slice as an independent sample, ignore spatial correlation along the slice axis, and can assign nearly identical scores to a perfectly consistent volume and to one where successive slices fluctuate arbitrarily. Although medical-domain feature extractors reduce the domain

gap, their embeddings are still computed on a slice-wise basis and therefore remain largely insensitive to through-plane continuity. These shortcomings indicate that neither voxel-based reference scores nor existing non-reference statistics faithfully quantify inter-slice consistency, which motivates developing dedicated metrics that explicitly encode through-plane smoothness, for instance by evaluating feature coherence across short slice sequences or by learning critics specialised for detecting through-plane flicker.

3.2.1. Referenced Quantitative Metrics

Referenced quantitative metrics measure pixel-level agreement between a synthetic image and its ground-truth counterpart, providing objective numbers that reflect fidelity when true reference data are available. The most commonly used metrics in this category are listed below.

Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR). This metric measures image fidelity based on pixel-wise intensity differences between generated and ground-truth images, with higher values indicating better reconstruction performance. It is defined as:

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{MAX}^2}{\text{MSE}} \right), \quad (2)$$

where:

- MAX is the maximum possible pixel value of the image (e.g., 1.0 for normalized images),
- MSE is the Mean Squared Error between I and \tilde{I} , defined as:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (I[i] - \tilde{I}[i])^2, \quad (3)$$

where N is the total number of pixels in the images.

Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) and Multi-Scale SSIM (MS-SSIM). SSIM decomposes perceptual similarity into *luminance*, *contrast*, and *structure* comparisons in local windows:

$$\text{SSIM}(I, \tilde{I}) = \underbrace{\frac{2\mu_I\mu_{\tilde{I}} + C_1}{\mu_I^2 + \mu_{\tilde{I}}^2 + C_1}}_{l(I, \tilde{I})} \cdot \underbrace{\frac{2\sigma_I\sigma_{\tilde{I}} + C_2}{\sigma_I^2 + \sigma_{\tilde{I}}^2 + C_2}}_{c(I, \tilde{I})} \cdot \underbrace{\frac{\sigma_{I\tilde{I}} + C_3}{\sigma_I\sigma_{\tilde{I}} + C_3}}_{s(I, \tilde{I})},$$

where $C_3 = C_2/2$. Here $l(\cdot)$, $c(\cdot)$, and $s(\cdot)$ are the **exact factors** that re-appear in MS-SSIM.

MS-SSIM evaluates those same three factors at multiple down-scaled versions of the images and combines them with user-chosen weights:

$$\text{MS-SSIM}(I, \tilde{I}) = \prod_{j=1}^M [l_j(I, \tilde{I})]^{\alpha_j} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^M [c_j(I, \tilde{I})]^{\beta_j} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^M [s_j(I, \tilde{I})]^{\gamma_j},$$

with l_j, c_j, s_j obtained by applying the same SSIM formulas above to the j -th scale (typically produced by Gaussian pyramids). Choosing exponents $\alpha_j, \beta_j, \gamma_j$ lets practitioners emphasize coarse-scale luminance or fine-scale structural fidelity, but the core quantities are directly inherited from the single-scale SSIM definition. The final score is the average over all local windows in the image.

Table 1: Methodological design space for diffusion-based volumetric synthesis.

Diffusion	Core idea	Advantages	Limitations
Native 3D	Run diffusion directly on full 3D voxel grids	Exact volumetric context; simplest pipeline	Cubic memory/compute; often down-sampled; requires super-computer scale
Latent 3D	Auto-encode the volume to a compact 3D latent grid, diffuse there, decode	10–100× lighter than native; still preserves 3D context	Needs a separate auto-encoder; compute can balloon for high-resolution latents; possible detail loss
Naïve 2D	Generate each 2D slice independently and stack	Minimal hardware	No inter-slice conditioning results in discontinuities; post-hoc fixes often required.
Consistency-aware 2D	2D model augmented with inter-slice links	Retains 2D efficiency and enforces volumetric coherence; focus of this review	Still lacks a full 3D field-of-view; extra architectural complexity

Table 2: Summary of recent native and latent 3D diffusion models. For cases involving multiple datasets, we report the image shape corresponding to the dataset with the highest voxel count. For models trained in multiple stages, we report the GPU with the highest resource requirement across all stages.

Native 3D Diffusion Models					
Name	Method	Max. Image Shape	Training GPU	Training Time	
Med-DDPM [23]	MRI synthesis conditioned on segmentation mask	128×128×128	80GB A100	3 days	
MC-DDPM [24]	Swin-VNet based MRI-to-CT synthesis	256×256×32	48GB RTX 6000	-	
3D-MedDiff [18]	MRI and CT synthesis using Coarse-to-fine cascaded 3D diffusion	512×512×512	2×80GB A100	8 days	
Cor2Vox [25]	Reconstruct CT using a Multi-stage UNet	64×64×64	48GB RTX A6000	6 days	
Latent Diffusion Models (LDMs)					
ALDM [26]	MRI synthesis using Anatomy-aware LDM with MS-SPADE blocks	256×256×150	4×80GB A100	-	
MAISI [27]	CT synthesis using Modular 3D LDM with MAISI-VAE, Diffusion, and ControlNet	512×512×768	8×80GB A100	25 days	
VCM [28]	MRI synthesis using Volumetric Conditioning Module on top of pretrained BrainLDM	160×160×192	24GB GPU	4 days	
Medical Diffusion [29]	MRI and CT synthesis using 3D VQ-GAN and LDM	128×128×128	24GB RTX 6000	7 days	
Tapp et al. [30]	MRI to CT translation using VAE and LDM	224×224×224	24GB A5000	-	

Table 3: Overview of Evaluation Metrics Used in Diffusion-Based Image Translation

Abbr.	Metric	Remarks
Referenced Image Metrics (RM)		
RM1	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR)	Pixel-wise fidelity; higher is better
RM2	Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM)	Perceptual similarity; bounded in [0,1]
RM3	Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	Mean absolute pixel difference
RM4	Mean Squared Error (MSE)	Mean squared pixel difference
RM5	Multi-Scale SSIM (MS-SSIM)	SSIM computed over multiple scales
Non-Referenced Image Metrics (NM)		
NM1	Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity (LPIPS)	Deep-feature perceptual distance; lower is better
NM2	Fréchet Inception Distance (FID)	Distribution distance between real and generated sets
NM3	Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD)	Kernel-based measure of distribution alignment
Downstream Task Metrics (DM)		
DM1	Dice Similarity Coefficient	Overlap ratio of segmentation masks
DM2	Intersection over Union (IoU)	Jaccard index for segmentation overlap
DM3	Hausdorff Distance (HD)	Maximum boundary deviation between masks
DM4	Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD)	Mean boundary distance between masks
DM5	Volumetric Overlap Error (VOE)	Complement of IoU; $1 - \text{IoU}$
Anatomical Metrics (AM)		
AM1	Brain-Volume Difference	Absolute difference in total brain volume
AM2	Spine-Curvature Correlation	Pearson correlation of predicted vs. ground-truth
AM3	Recovery Rate	Task-specific anatomical recovery percentage
AM4	Standardized Uptake Value (SUV)	PET tracer uptake quantification
AM5	Mean Cortical Thickness	Average cortical thickness across regions

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Squared Error (MSE). The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) computes the average absolute pixel-wise difference between a generated image \tilde{I} and its ground-truth counterpart I :

$$\text{MAE}(I, \tilde{I}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |I[i] - \tilde{I}[i]|, \quad (4)$$

where N is the total number of pixels, and $I[i]$ and $\tilde{I}[i]$ denote the intensities of the i -th pixel in the ground-truth and generated images, respectively.

The Mean Squared Error (MSE) uses the squared differences instead, penalizing larger deviations more strongly:

$$\text{MSE}(I, \tilde{I}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (I[i] - \tilde{I}[i])^2. \quad (5)$$

3.2.2. Non-Referenced Quantitative Metrics

Non-referenced metrics estimate perceptual quality and detect artefacts directly from the synthetic image itself, without relying on ground-truth data for comparison. The most commonly used metrics in this category are listed below.

Maximum-Mean Discrepancy (MMD). This metric measures the distance between distributions of synthetic and real images and does not require pixel-wise ground truth. It is defined as:

$$\text{MMD}^2(I, \tilde{I}) = \mathbb{E}_{I, I'} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{P}} [k(I, I')] + \mathbb{E}_{\tilde{I}, \tilde{I}'} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{Q}} [k(\tilde{I}, \tilde{I}')] - 2 \mathbb{E}_{I \sim \mathcal{P}, \tilde{I} \sim \mathcal{Q}} [k(I, \tilde{I})]$$

where:

- I are real images sampled from the distribution \mathcal{P} ,
- \tilde{I} are synthetic images sampled from the distribution \mathcal{Q} ,
- $k(I, \tilde{I})$ is a kernel function (e.g., Gaussian kernel) that maps inputs to a higher-dimensional space to measure similarity,
- \mathbb{E} is the expectation operator, representing averages over the respective distributions,
- I, I' are pairs of real images drawn from \mathcal{P} ,
- \tilde{I}, \tilde{I}' are pairs of synthetic images drawn from \mathcal{Q} .

Fréchet Inception Distance (FID). This metric compares the distributions of generated and real images using learned features from a neural network. It is defined as:

$$\text{FID}(I, \tilde{I}) = \|\mu_I - \mu_{\tilde{I}}\|_2^2 + \text{Tr}(\Sigma_I + \Sigma_{\tilde{I}} - 2(\Sigma_I \Sigma_{\tilde{I}})^{\frac{1}{2}})$$

where:

- I are real images,
- \tilde{I} are synthetic images,
- μ_I and $\mu_{\tilde{I}}$ are the mean feature vectors of real and synthetic images, respectively, computed from a pre-trained neural network,
- Σ_I and $\Sigma_{\tilde{I}}$ are the covariance matrices of the features from real and synthetic images, respectively,
- $\|\mu_I - \mu_{\tilde{I}}\|_2^2$ is the squared Euclidean distance between the mean feature vectors,
- $\text{Tr}(\cdot)$ is the trace operator, which computes the sum of the diagonal elements of a matrix,
- $(\Sigma_I \Sigma_{\tilde{I}})^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is the matrix square root of the product of the covariance matrices.

Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity (LPIPS). LPIPS quantifies perceptual similarity between a generated image \tilde{I} and its ground-truth counterpart I by comparing deep feature representations extracted from a pre-trained convolutional neural network. The distance is computed as

$$\text{LPIPS}(I, \tilde{I}) = \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{1}{H_l W_l} \sum_{h=1}^{H_l} \sum_{w=1}^{W_l} \|w_l \odot (\hat{f}_l^I(h, w) - \hat{f}_l^{\tilde{I}}(h, w))\|_2^2$$

where

- L is the number of considered feature layers,
- $f_l^I, f_l^{\tilde{I}} \in \mathbb{R}^{C_l \times H_l \times W_l}$ are the feature maps of I and \tilde{I} at layer l ,
- \hat{f}_l denotes channel-wise unit-normalized features,
- H_l and W_l are the height and width of the layer's feature map,
- $w_l \in \mathbb{R}^{C_l}$ are learned, layer-specific channel weights,
- \odot is the element-wise (Hadamard) product.

Lower LPIPS values indicate higher perceptual similarity, aligning well with human visual judgment while remaining sensitive to subtle structural and textural differences.

3.2.3. Downstream and Anatomical Metrics

Downstream task metrics such as Dice or Hausdorff Distance (HD) gauge how well synthetic images support subsequent applications such as segmentation. Anatomical metrics instead compare biologically meaningful measurements (e.g., mean cortical thickness, ventricular volume) between synthetic and real images, testing whether clinically relevant structures are faithfully preserved.

4. Categorization of 2D Methods

In this section we arrange the 2D approaches that address inter-slice inconsistency in volumetric diffusion into three conceptual categories, shown in Figures 4–6: condition-guided, architectural, and post-generation optimisation. Condition-guided methods supply explicit slice-aligned cues such as slice index, viewing angle, or anatomy statistics so adjacent slices share the same guidance. Architectural methods weave consistency into the network itself through mechanisms like multi-view fusion, or shared latent variables. Post-generation approaches first synthesize slices and then apply a global refinement such as total-variation term. The boundaries between categories are soft; for example, Diff-Ensembler [31] concatenates 3D priors and could be classed as condition-guided, yet its main novelty is a learnable fusion architecture, so it is listed with architectural methods; DiffGEPIC [32] refines one view using two others and might resemble a post-generation tweak, but the refinement occurs inside the forward pass and is therefore treated as an architectural choice; SC-BBDM applies style-key histogram conditioning that looks condition-guided, but its inter-slice trajectory alignment (ISTA) runs only after sampling, so it fits best in the post-generation optimisation bucket. Unless explicitly illustrated otherwise, all methods begin inference from 2D or 3D noise that may be guided by auxiliary signals.

4.1. Condition-Guided Methods

Condition-guided diffusion methods refer to techniques that inject auxiliary information such as class labels, segmentation maps, or other modalities into the diffusion process to control or steer the generation toward specific outputs. These methods modify the denoising network by incorporating additional data, which are often first transformed into

suitable representations through feature extraction or embedding techniques (e.g., positional encodings, learned embeddings). The conditioned information is then integrated with the diffusion model via mechanisms such as concatenation with the input at specific layers, or through cross-attention blocks that allow the model to focus dynamically on the guiding signal during generation. This guidance enables the diffusion model to produce outputs that align with external constraints or desired attributes. Figure 4 shows all such methods.

X-Diffusion [33] introduces a cross-sectional strategy that treats 3D reconstruction as a sequence of conditioned slice predictions across arbitrary orientations and uses multi-view fusion to generate anatomically consistent, high-resolution volumes from as little as a single 2D slice. The proposed method first trained a latent diffusion model on 2D axial slices extracted from randomly rotated 3D volumes, learning to denoise each slice while conditioning on the rotation parameters and the slice’s relative position within the volume. Next, during inference, the model iterates over a set of predefined viewing angles; for each angle it denoises noisy slice representations conditioned on the slice-specific information, thereby producing a complete stack of slices in that orientation. These slices are assembled into a 3D volume aligned to the current view and subsequently realigned to a canonical orientation. The same procedure is repeated for all viewing angles, and the resulting canonical volumes are averaged to yield a single, high-fidelity 3D reconstruction.

GEM-3D [34] presents a conditional 3D synthesis framework that leverages a single “informed slice” to inject patient-specific anatomy and appearance into the generative process. The proposed method generated 3D volume by sequentially generating smaller axial subvolumes in an autoregressive fashion. First, it samples a random 2D informed slice from the available 3D dataset; this slice inherently captures the patient’s anatomical features, positional context, and scanning parameters and can even be synthetically generated. It is encoded with a variational autoencoder, and the same encoding step is repeated for every slice in the window. Next, the corresponding mask volume is encoded separately. The informed-slice latent, the mask latent, and a noisy image latent are then concatenated and passed to a latent diffusion model, which denoises the combined representation and decodes it into a complete 3D image volume.

Blaze3DM [35] introduces a tri-plane diffusion framework that generates high-fidelity volumetric images through a compact 2.5D representation. The proposed method proceeds as follows. First, it constructs a tri-plane feature tensor by sampling random voxels from the target volume, projecting them onto sagittal, coronal, and axial planes, and concatenating the resulting feature maps. Next, it learns a coordinate-based decoder that maps any 3D point to an intensity value via bilinear sampling from the tri-plane features followed by a lightweight decoding network. Afterwards, the diffusion process is performed directly in the tri-plane feature space, with positional embeddings conditioning each denoising step of the DDPM.

The Conditional Diffusion Probabilistic Model (cDPM) [36] introduces a memory-efficient framework that learns inter-slice dependencies from arbitrary combinations of 2D slices to synthesize full 3D volumes. First, a 2D conditional denoising diffusion probabilistic model is trained to generate randomly selected target slices from noisy inputs while conditioning on another randomly chosen set of slices from the same volume. Next, during each training iteration, the algorithm samples new condition and target index sets, applies the forward diffusion process to the target slices, and employs an attention-augmented UNet to estimate noise residuals, thereby capturing relationships between non-contiguous slices. Afterwards, in the inference stage, the model generates an initial batch of slices from pure noise without any conditioning. Finally, it iteratively synthesizes subsequent batches of

slices conditioned on the volumes produced so far, repeating this process until an entire 3D volume is reconstructed.

DMCVR [37] is a diffusion-based framework that reconstructs full 3D cardiac volumes from sparsely sampled 2D cine images. The proposed method started by encoding each acquired 2D slice into three latent spaces: a global semantic latent produced by a UNet-based encoder, a regional morphology latent obtained from a segmentation-style encoder that captures anatomical shapes, and a stochastic latent representing noise. Next, for every pair of adjacent slices, the semantic and morphology latents are linearly interpolated while the stochastic latents undergo spherical interpolation; the resulting latent triplets are fed into a conditional generator that synthesizes the missing intermediate slices. Afterwards, all real and generated slices are stacked to reconstruct the complete 3D volume.

Slice-Based LDM (SBLDM) [38] incorporates both spatial context and tumor-specific cues to produce anatomically consistent images with a latent diffusion model. The input medical image is concatenated with its corresponding tumor mask and encoded into a shared latent representation. Next, summary statistics describing the tumor are embedded and fused with positional information to provide explicit guidance about lesion characteristics and slice location. These combined embeddings steer the latent diffusion process, leading to the generation of the final, tumor-aware image.

Across these six works several complementary advances emerge. X-Diffusion reformulates 3D reconstruction as slice-wise conditioned denoising with rotation- and position-aware guidance and a multi-view fusion stage. GEM-3D introduces the informed slice as a lightweight patient-specific prior and combines mask-conditioned diffusion with autoregressive sub-volume generation. cDPM demonstrates memory-efficient reconstruction by conditioning on arbitrary slice subsets through an attention mechanism that captures long-range dependencies. DMCVR blends semantic, morphological, and stochastic latents with mixed interpolation strategies to fill gaps between sparse acquisitions. SBLDM fuses positional information with tumour statistics inside the latent space, producing anatomically faithful, lesion-aware volumes.

Blaze3DM offers a complementary solution: it compresses the volume into sagittal, coronal and axial feature planes, performs diffusion in this tri-plane space and relies on a small coordinate decoder to recover voxel intensities, achieving high fidelity with the lightest memory footprint among the group. SC-BBDM [13] likewise introduces a style-key vector built from the target-modality histogram to match contrast. Together these contributions illustrate three complementary levers for enforcing inter-slice coherence: explicit conditioning on shared cues, architectural designs that aggregate cross-slice information, and learned fusion strategies that combine multiple predictions into a consistent whole.

4.2. Methods with Architectural Novelties

Methods with architectural novelties focus on modifying the internal structure of the network to improve performance and inter-slice consistency, without relying on external conditioning. These approaches include adding specialized layers or modules for tasks like multi-view training, where the network processes multiple anatomical views (e.g., axial, coronal, sagittal) through parallel branches or shared-weight encoders. Others adopt alternative data representations such as tri-plane representations, which model 3D volumes using three orthogonal 2D feature planes, enabling efficient generation and reducing the memory demands of full volumetric processing. Additional architectural changes may involve integrating view-fusion layers or hierarchical processing blocks to better capture spatial relationships and structural consistency. These modifications enhance the model’s ability to learn from

Figure 4: Condition-Guided Methods. (1) X-Diffusion: conditioned on rotation angle and slice position. (2) Gem-3D: conditioned on 2D image and mask priors. (3) Blaze3DM carries out diffusion in a tri-plane representation of the volume. (4) cDPM: conditioned on randomly selected 2D slices. (5) DMCVR: conditioned on interpolated latent segmentation and semantic priors. (6) SBLDM: conditioned on tumor statistics and slice location.

complex inputs and generate high-quality outputs through structural innovation rather than external guidance.

Make-A-Volume [39] extends 2D latent diffusion to coherent 3D synthesis by explicitly modeling interactions across adjacent slices. The proposed method started with a normally trained 2D latent diffusion model for individual image slice generation. The model is later reconfigured to accept a batch containing multiple slices at once, and one-dimensional convolutional layers are inserted into the autoencoder so that features can be shared along the volume’s Z-axis. Finally, the modified network is fine-tuned end-to-end, enabling it to produce complete 3D volumes rather than independent slices.

Multi-view Averaging Diffusion Mode (MADM) [40] combines a fast 3D prior with lightweight slice-wise diffusion to reconstruct high-quality PET volumes from low-count inputs. The pipeline can be divided into three phases: (i) a 3D convolutional network is trained to produce a one-step prior image directly from the noisy, low-count PET scan, (ii) Gaussian noise is added to this prior to initialize the diffusion process at a chosen timestep, (iii) three independent 2D diffusion models operating in axial, coronal, and sagittal planes, denoise their respective slice stacks in parallel, capturing contextual information within each view and (iv) at every denoising step the slice-wise outputs from the three views are averaged to yield a spatially coherent 3D estimate, and the procedure iterates until convergence.

Diff-Ensembler [31] ensembles independently trained 2D diffusion models to translate 3D medical volumes. To achieve this, the authors first trained two 2D denoising diffusion probabilistic models separately on orthogonal planes of the target domain, such as axial and sagittal slices. During inference, they began each denoising iteration by having the pre-trained 2D models generate noise estimates and hierarchical feature maps for their respective planes. Lastly, they feed these outputs, together with the current noisy 3D volume and the original input volume, into a 3D fusion network, which predicts voxel-wise weights and a residual correction to form a unified noise estimate for the entire volume. This fused estimate drives the next denoising step, and the cycle repeats until the volume is fully refined.

Two Perpendicular Diffusion Model (TPDM) [41] enforces structural coherence in 3D image synthesis by coordinating two slice-wise diffusion models trained on orthogonal views. The method begins by training two independent 2D denoising diffusion probabilistic models separately on perpendicular planes of the training volumes e.g. axial and sagittal slices, so that each model captures in-plane statistics along its own orientation. Next, during inference, the denoising process alternates between the two models every K steps: one model performs K diffusion steps on its view, the result is reshaped into the full volume, and control is passed to the other model for the next K steps along the orthogonal view. This alternating schedule continues until all timesteps are exhausted, allowing information to propagate back and forth across directions and promoting inter-slice consistency without ever training a full 3D network.

Denoising Diffusion Model for Gradient Echo Plural Contrast Imaging (DiffGEPCI) [32] generates multi-contrast MRI volumes by coupling full-plane synthesis with orthogonal-plane refinement. At the outset, a single 2D conditional denoising diffusion probabilistic model is trained on axial, coronal, and sagittal slices, with multi-Gradient-Recalled Echo (mGRE) signals serving as conditioning input. Next, during inference, the model reconstructs an initial 3D volume slice-by-slice along the axial plane through a 1000-step reverse diffusion process. The next step deals with re-orienting this axial volume into coronal and sagittal stacks; each stack receives ten forward diffusion steps to introduce mild noise and ten reverse steps with the same model to refine the slices in its respective plane. The process concludes with fusing the three plane-specific volumes by averaging voxel intensities,

yielding the final high-quality output.

These five studies explore architectural alterations that let slice-wise diffusion recover the spatial coherence of full 3D models while keeping a 2D-level resource budget. Make-A-Volume keeps the recipe almost unchanged, simply grouping more slices per batch and inserting 1D convolutions so neighbouring latents communicate. MADM, TPDM and DiffGEPCI adopt a multi-view strategy, training separate 2D models on axial, coronal and sagittal planes. At inference time they allow these orthogonal views to interact in distinct ways: MADM averages the three outputs at every step, TPDM alternates K denoising steps between the two perpendicular models, and DiffGEPCI carries out a long axial reverse pass followed by short forward-and-reverse refinements in the other planes. All three propagate context through the stack without ever building a dense 3D tensor, enabling rapid PET or multi-contrast MRI reconstruction on a single high-end GPU. Diff-Ensembler shows that pre-trained 2D models can be combined by a dedicated 3D fusion network that learns voxel-wise mixtures of their score estimates. Together these works show that 1D feature sharing, orthogonal-view cooperation and tri-plane compression, combined with a lightweight global prior, can narrow the quality gap to native 3D diffusion while keeping memory and compute demands firmly in the 2D regime.

4.3. Methods with Post-Generation Optimization

Methods that use post-generation optimization in diffusion models apply optimization-based techniques after generation to enforce structural consistency. Unlike architectural or conditioning approaches, these methods operate either after the entire diffusion process has produced an initial output or at the end of each diffusion step. These post-generation optimization steps refine the output by imposing cross-slice consistency constraints, improving the realism and anatomical plausibility of the volumes without modifying the diffusion model or its training.

SC-BBDM [13] translates CT to MRI with a 2D Brownian-Bridge diffusion backbone while enforcing slice-to-slice coherence through Inter-Slice Trajectory Alignment (ISTA). This approach unfolds in the following steps. First, a multi-slice Brownian Bridge model is trained. Then at inference time the model predicts noise for overlapping windows of slices; ISTA’s co-prediction phase averages these overlapping noise estimates so neighbouring slices agree on the direction of the next diffusion step. Lastly, a deterministic correction phase refines the co-predicted volume with a score-based update that nudges every slice back onto the learned data manifold, eliminating residual discontinuities.

Model-based Iterative Reconstruction Diffusion (DiffusionMBIR) [42] merges a slice-trained diffusion prior with an alternating direction solver to enforce measurement fidelity and smoothness across slices. The proposed method proceeds as follows. First, a 2D diffusion model is trained on individual slices of the target domain. Next, during inference, each denoising step is followed by a single Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM) update that aggregates the current slice stack into a provisional 3D volume, enforces consistency with the measured data, and applies a total-variation (TV) prior along the z-axis to suppress inter-slice noise while preserving sharp edges. Afterwards, the introduced auxiliary variables are carried forward to the next iteration, enabling information sharing across the full reconstruction process. This cycle of diffusion denoising and ADMM+TV correction repeats until convergence.

These two methods highlight the significance of pairing 2D diffusion backbones with task-specific optimisation loops to recover volumetric consistency. SC-BBDM leverages ISTA’s predictor–corrector

Figure 5: Methods with Architectural Novelties. (1) Make-a-Volume adds 1D convolution layers on top of a 2D LDM to emit full volumes. (2) MADM trains three axis-specific 2D DDPMs and averages their outputs. (3) Diff-Ensembler: conditioned on two 2D priors trained on the target domain. (4) TPDM alternates denoising between two perpendicular 2D DDPMs to enforce cross-view consistency. (5) DiffGEPCI uses one mGRE-conditioned 2D cDDPM to generate an axial stack, lightly refine coronal and sagittal views, and average the three results into the final 3D volume.

coupling of overlapping slice predictions to obtain anatomically coherent stacks without the memory cost of full 3D diffusion. DiffusionMBIR shows that embedding a pretrained diffusion prior inside an ADMM framework, reinforced with through-plane TV regularisation, can simultaneously honour measurement data and promote smoothness. Collectively, they exemplify a broader design trend: augmenting efficient slice-wise diffusion with domain-aware correction modules enables high-fidelity 3D reconstructions while retaining the compute footprint of 2D models.

5. Comparison and Discussion

5.1. Computational Resources

Table 4 lists the image shape, GPU specifications, training and inference times, and the evaluation metrics used in each paper (to be detailed in the next subsection).

Figure 7 complements the table and compares GPU memory requirements against normalized input sizes for different classes of diffusion-based models. Overall, 3D Native methods (red circles) exhibit the steepest scaling trend, requiring memory in the range of 40–150 GB as input size grows, making them less practical for resource-constrained environments. Among these, models like MedDiff-FM and 3D-MedDiff occupy the upper-right region, reflecting the cost of voxel-level processing across all dimensions.

In contrast, 3D Latent Diffusion Models (orange circles) significantly mitigate memory demand by operating in a compressed latent space. These models achieve moderate memory footprints (15–60 GB) even for large normalized volumes, demonstrating improved scalability compared to 3D Native approaches, though memory growth still persists as input size increases.

2D approaches form three sub-categories and exhibit a distinct pattern. Condition-guided methods (dark blue triangles) and architectural variations (mid-blue pentagons) maintain memory usage below 30 GB across a broad range of normalized input sizes, while post-generation optimization strategies (light blue stars) push efficiency further, achieving sub-10 GB footprints (e.g., MADM). When aggregated as a group, 2D methods tend toward the lower-right region of the plot, offering the most favorable trade-off by handling relatively larger inputs while maintaining lower memory consumption compared to 3D methods.

5.2. Metrics

Table 4 provides a comparative overview of methods, organized into categories. For each paper, the table lists the evaluation metrics reported, input image dimensions, GPU requirements, and training or inference durations, enabling quick assessment of methodological focus and computational demands.

The reviewed diffusion-based methods for medical image synthesis utilize a diverse set of evaluation metrics, reflecting the multifaceted nature of image quality and clinical relevance. Most methods report standard referenced metrics such as PSNR (RM_1) and SSIM (RM_2), which assess pixel-level fidelity relative to ground truth. Some works, such as Make-A-Volume and MADM, further incorporate MAE (RM_3) or MSE (RM_4), providing additional insights into reconstruction errors. A few advanced methods like cDPM and Diff-Ensembler also report MS-SSIM (RM_5), emphasizing the preservation of structural information. In addition to these, several condition-guided methods adopt non-referenced metrics such as LPIPS (NM_1), FID (NM_2), and MMD (NM_3), which aim to quantify perceptual quality and sample realism without relying on paired ground truth.

Downstream task analysis plays a crucial role in validating the utility of synthesized images for clinical or diagnostic purposes. Many methods evaluate their performance using Dice (DM_1) and IoU (DM_2), which are standard metrics in segmentation tasks. Some methods such as GEM-3D and DMCVR extend this evaluation using Hausdorff Distance (DM_3), Average Symmetric Surface Distance (DM_4), and Volume Overlap Error (DM_5), offering a more comprehensive view of geometric and boundary accuracy. A smaller set of methods also reports anatomical metrics like Brain Volume Difference (AM_1), Spine Curvature Correlation (AM_2), Standardized Uptake Value (AM_4), and Mean Cortical Thickness (AM_5), emphasizing biological plausibility and relevance to downstream clinical workflows. These choices often align with the intended application of each method, with condition-guided methods favoring more task-aware evaluations.

5.3. Discussion and Future Directions

Recent work shows that giving a slice-wise diffusion model even a small hint about neighbouring slices often improves volume quality more than making the network itself much larger. Methods such as SC-BBDM [13] and X-Diffusion [33] inject masks, histogram cues, or attention links across slices so that each slice stays aligned with the one before and after it. When those hints are absent, adding extra layers or cross-view mechanisms inside the network can still help, but usually at a higher training or sampling cost.

Most approaches fall into one of two camps. Early-fusion systems such as cDPM [36], GEM-3D [34], and SBLDM [38] blend the hint and the slice at the first denoising step, completing generation in a single pass. Late-fusion systems such as Diff-Ensembler [31] or DiffGEM [32] first create several partial volumes (for example one per view) and merge them gradually; this caps peak memory but stretches inference time, so the preferred strategy depends on the available GPU budget.

Figure 7 shows that memory-friendly tricks such as tri-plane features, latent diffusion, and multi-view averaging push many 2D methods into the lower-right quadrant, where larger inputs can be handled with modest memory. Native 3D or hybrid models still win when sub-millimetre fidelity over a large field of view is mandatory, but their lead is shrinking as 2D consistency modules mature and latent-3D pipelines gain traction.

Slice-wise diffusion’s main bottleneck is the sheer number of forward passes: a 512^3 stack requires 512 denoising trajectories unless neighbouring views are shared. Late-fusion pipelines reduce peak memory but demand orchestration of multiple UNets and alignment modules, adding I/O latency. By contrast, tri-plane diffusion compresses the volume into three orthogonal feature planes and is reported to run more than 20× faster than full-3D baselines while keeping artefacts in check. Latent-3D models such as ALDM and MAISI occupy the middle ground: they operate on volumetric latents and therefore scale better than native 3D, yet still preserve the through-plane context that pure 2D models may miss.

When only a single 24 GB card is available and turnaround time matters, a lightweight 2D approach such as MADM or Blaze3DM is pragmatic. If 48–80 GB cards are accessible, latent 3D models can accommodate large clinical fields of view, and native 3D remains an option for applications like radiotherapy planning where sub-voxel accuracy is critical. Under ultra-tight latency constraints (for example intra-operative MRI) tri-plane backbones currently offer the best balance between memory, throughput, and coherence.

Emerging techniques first devised to maintain temporal coherence in video diffusion provide a transferable blueprint for enforcing inter-slice consistency in volumetric imaging. Video diffusion tackles

Figure 6: Methods with Post-Generation Optimization. These methods rely on post-generation optimisation to clean up the model’s output. (1) DiffusionMBIR Uses an ADMM-based model-based iterative reconstruction (MBIR) loop after a 2D DDPM reconstructs the volume, to enforce TV-style smoothness across slices. (2) SC-BBDM uses a Brownian-Bridge Diffusion Model conditioned on image histogram, as well as ISTA slice-alignment to refine the output for inter-slice consistency.

Table 4: Summary of 2D Diffusion-Based Methods. Evaluation metric abbreviations are defined in Table 3

Paper	Metrics	Image Shape	GPU	Duration
Condition-Guided Diffusion Based Methods				
X-Diffusion[33]	$RM_1, RM_2, NM_1, DM_1, AM_1, AM_2$	240x240x155	48GB	train: - inference: 2.5min
GEM-3D [34]	NM_1, NM_2, DM_1, DM_3	512x512x100	8x32GB	train: 7 days inference: -
Blaze3DM[35]	RM_1, RM_2	256x256x256	24GB	train: - inference: 48min
eDPM[36]	RM_5, NM_2, NM_3	128x128x128	80GB	train: - inference: -
DMCVR [37]	$RM_1, RM_2, DM_1, DM_5, DM_3, DM_4$	-	4x48GB	train: 3.8 days inference: -
SBLDM[38]	RM_1, RM_2, DM_1, DM_2	192x192x96	48GB	train: - inference: 30.9s
Methods using Architectural Novelties				
Make-A-Volume[39]	RM_1, RM_2, RM_3	256x256x35	80GB	train: - inference: -
MADM[40]	RM_1, RM_2, RM_4, AM_4	192x192x460	6.4GB	train: - inference: 30min
Diff-Ensembler [31]	$RM_1, RM_2, NM_2, NM_3, DM_1, AM_3$	192x192x512	40GB	train: 32 days inference: 2.3min
TPDM[41]	RM_1, RM_2, AM_5	256x256x256	-	train: - inference: -
DiffGEPCI[32]	RM_1, RM_2	256x192x85	-	train: - inference: -
Methods using Post-Generation Optimization				
DiffusionMBIR[42]	RM_1, RM_2	256x256x154	24GB	train: 0.5 week inference: -
SC-BBDM[13]	RM_1, RM_2, RM_4	176x176x160	48GB	train: - inference: -

Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Data Availability

No new data were generated in this study. Data underlying the results are available within the cited publications.

Declaration of AI Use

The manuscript was written by the authors. ChatGPT (OpenAI GPT-5) was used only to assist with light language polishing and improving readability. The ideas, scientific content, and analysis were developed and organized by the authors, who also verified all references and take full responsibility for the accuracy and conclusions of the work.

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